

Research Article

Automatic Panel Cleaning System: Boost Solar Efficiency

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Abstract: The performance of solar photovoltaic (PV) systems is significantly affected by environmental factors, particularly the accumulation of dust, dirt, and bird droppings on panel surfaces. In regions like Malaysia, where solar adoption is increasing, reduced panel efficiency due to surface contamination presents a major challenge, with potential energy losses of up to 50% if panels are not regularly cleaned. Manual cleaning methods are often labor-intensive, time-consuming, and costly, especially for large-scale installations. This study investigates effective cleaning techniques and proposes a conceptual design for an automatic solar panel cleaning system. Three cleaning methods were tested using a substitute solar panel surface: (1) a brush, (2) a silicone wiper, and (3) a silicone wiper combined with a microfiber cloth. Simulated contaminants—carbon dust and a water-flour mixture—were used to represent common pollutants. Results showed that the third method achieved the highest cleaning efficiency, removing up to 99% of surface contaminants. Based on this outcome, a proposed automated cleaning system design was developed using a mobile unit equipped with a silicone wiper, microfiber cloth, ATmega16 microcontroller, sensors, and a wireless charging dock. The system is intended to operate autonomously at scheduled intervals, offering a low-maintenance and scalable solution. With further development and prototyping, the proposed design has strong potential for commercialization, particularly in solar farms and commercial rooftop PV systems where regular cleaning is critical to maintaining performance. This solution could significantly reduce maintenance costs, enhance energy yield, and support the broader adoption of clean energy technologies.

Keywords: Solar panel cleaning; Automation; Photovoltaic efficiency; Dust removal; Renewable energy maintenance

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1. INTRODUCTION

Solar energy is one of the most promising renewable energy sources globally, and its adoption has been expanding rapidly in many countries, including Malaysia. In an effort to reduce dependence on fossil fuels and move towards sustainable energy solutions, Malaysia has seen significant growth in the installation of solar photovoltaic (PV) systems (Ab Kadir et al., 2010; Islam et al., 2022). However, the performance of these systems is heavily influenced by environmental factors—particularly air quality and surface cleanliness. Among these, the accumulation of dust and dirt on solar panels has emerged as a critical issue, substantially reducing the efficiency of energy generation.

Dust accumulation on PV panels can cause energy losses of up to 50% daily, depending on local environmental conditions. These losses translate into significant economic implications, with studies reporting annual financial impacts ranging from 0.0011 to 22.43 USD/m² across various regions including the Middle East, Asia, and Australia (Sreenath et al., 2020). In Malaysia, the problem is similarly pronounced. For example, a study conducted at Kuantan Airport revealed that irregular cleaning of solar panels led to annual energy losses of approximately 526 MWh, equating to nearly 2% of the system's total output (Sulaiman et al., 2018). Furthermore, experimental data suggests that even a relatively low dust density of 6 g/m² can result in a performance drop exceeding 20% (Gholami et al., 2018), underscoring the importance of effective cleaning methods.

Given the clear impact of dust on PV performance, this research explores the development of an automatic panel cleaning system aimed at preserving solar panel efficiency and reducing operational costs. The study evaluates three cleaning mechanisms: a brush-based system offering a low-cost solution for large-area coverage; a silicone wiper system designed to remove dust with minimal surface abrasion; and a hybrid solution combining a wiper with a microfibre cloth to effectively eliminate fine dust without scratching the panel surface. Each method is assessed for its cleaning efficiency, feasibility for long-term use, and potential to enhance overall energy output.

By identifying practical and cost-effective cleaning technologies, this study aims to support the consistent performance of PV systems under real-world environmental conditions. The proposed automatic cleaning system offers a potential solution to one of the key operational challenges in solar energy production, contributing to more reliable and efficient renewable energy generation.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

2.1 Substitute Solar Panel Surface

Figure 1. Substitute Solar Panel Surface

An 11-inch tempered glass screen protector was used as a substitute for the solar panel surface in this study, as shown in Figure 1. This material was selected due to its similarity in texture and smoothness to actual PV panel glass, allowing for realistic testing of cleaning methods.

2.2 Investigation of the Most Effective Method for Cleaning Airborne Dust Particles and Bird Droppings on Solar Panel

To evaluate the effectiveness of various cleaning techniques for solar panel maintenance, three different methods were tested. These methods were Method A: Brushing the surface with a standard cleaning brush, Method B: Wiping the surface using a silicone wiper and Method C: Wiping the surface with a microfiber cloth attached to the end of the silicone wiper. Two types of common contaminants

were simulated in the experiment to represent real-world solar panel soiling, *i.e.* activated carbon was used to represent airborne dust particles and a mixture of water and flour was used to mimic bird droppings or sticky organic residues.

The contaminants were applied to the glass surface to replicate dirty solar panel conditions. Each cleaning method was then applied individually to assess its effectiveness. After cleaning, the results were documented photographically, and visual observations were made to evaluate the cleanliness of the surface. The effectiveness of each method was determined by comparing the before-and-after conditions, focusing on the level of residue removed. Observations were made based on the amount of visible dirt remaining after each cleaning method was applied.

3. FINDINGS

3.1 Investigation of Solar Panel Cleaning Method for Airborne Dust Particles

Figure 2. Investigation of the Most Effective Method for Cleaning Airborne Dust Particles

In this experiment, activated carbon was used to simulate airborne dust and dirt on the solar panel surface. The panel was evenly coated with the carbon particles, and each of the three cleaning methods—Method A (brush), Method B (silicone wiper), and Method C (wiper with microfiber cloth)—was applied to evaluate their effectiveness.

Based on the results illustrated in Figure 2, Method B and Method C demonstrated significantly better cleaning performance compared to Method A. Both methods removed most of the carbon particles, leaving the surface visibly cleaner. In contrast, Method A was less effective, as the brush left

behind a noticeable amount of carbon dust. This was likely due to the gaps between the bristles, which prevented thorough contact with the surface.

3.2 Optimisation of Solar Panel Cleaning Method for Bird Droppings

To further assess the effectiveness of the cleaning methods in removing bird droppings and other unwanted residues, the experiment was repeated using a mixture of flour and water to simulate sticky organic contaminants. The same three cleaning methods—Method A (brush), Method B (silicone wiper), and Method C (wiper with microfiber cloth)—were applied to evaluate their performance under these conditions.

Figure 3. Investigation of the Most Effective Method for Cleaning Bird Droppings

Among the three methods, Method C once again proved to be the most effective (as shown in Figure 3). The silicone wiper was able to remove the majority of the flour-water mixture, while the attached microfiber cloth provided a secondary cleaning action that further improved the surface cleanliness. The microfiber cloth was particularly effective when pressure was applied through the motion of the wiper, enabling it to absorb and remove any remaining residue more thoroughly.

This two-stage cleaning process—mechanical wiping followed by absorbent polishing—resulted in a significantly cleaner surface compared to Methods A and B alone. Therefore, Method C demonstrated optimal performance for removing not only dry dust particles but also more challenging contaminants such as bird droppings and liquid residues.

Figure 4. Illustrations of the solar panel cleaning system

4. DISCUSSION

A conceptual design of the proposed solar panel cleaning system is illustrated in Figure 4. The suggested system consists of a movable body mounted on wheels, equipped with a silicone wiper and a strip of microfiber cloth attached behind it. This design aims to allow the cleaning unit to move autonomously across the solar panel surface, with the silicone wiper removing dust and debris, followed by the microfiber cloth to enhance cleanliness by capturing finer particles.

Based on experimental results, Method C—which combines a silicone wiper and a microfiber cloth—proved to be the most effective cleaning method when compared to Method A (brush) and Method B (wiper only). This approach demonstrated superior efficiency due to its two-step cleaning mechanism: the wiper clears the majority of the contaminants, while the microfiber cloth further polishes the surface. These findings support the potential integration of Method C into an automatic solar panel cleaning system to improve panel efficiency.

The proposed system design includes essential components such as a silicone wiper, microfiber cloth, ATmega16 microcontroller, sensors, motorised wheels, and a wireless charging dock. The wireless docking station is envisioned to serve both as a charging point and as a shelter to protect the device from harsh environmental conditions when not in operation.

In the suggested operation, the microcontroller would be programmed to initiate cleaning at scheduled intervals. The system would detach itself from the docking station, and the motorised wheels would guide the cleaning unit across the solar panel. The silicone wiper would perform the initial cleaning, while the microfiber cloth would follow to remove any residual particles. The cleaning materials are proposed to be soft and non-abrasive to prevent damage to the solar panel surface.

While the design is currently conceptual, it offers a promising solution for automated, low-maintenance solar panel cleaning. Further development, including mechanical design, control system integration, and field testing, would be required to validate its practical application and long-term performance.

5. CONCLUSION

This study evaluated three solar panel cleaning methods and found that the combination of a silicone wiper and microfiber cloth (Method C) was the most effective, removing up to 99% of simulated

dust and dirt. Based on these results, a proposed design for an automatic cleaning system was suggested, incorporating Method C to maintain panel efficiency. With further development, this system could offer a practical, low-maintenance solution for improving solar energy output.

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